

COMPRESSIVE PROPERTY REINFORCEMENT OF UNIDIRECTIONAL FRP BY FILAMENT COVER METHOD

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ABSTRACT

A covered ultra high molecular weight polyethylene fiber bundle by filament yarn was designed, the compressive failure behavior of unidirectional fiber-reinforced epoxy matrix composites containing covered fibers has been investigated. There were significant increase in compressive strength and modulus was noted for the case of covered fiber bundle/epoxy composite, compared with the unidirectional fiber bundle/epoxy composite. The compression damage modes of tested specimens were observed, with the presence of fiber bulking, bundle bulking and longitudinal splitting.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composite materials consist of fibers of high strength and modulus embedded in or bonded to a matrix with distinct interfaces between them. In general, fibers are the principal load-carrying members, while the surrounding matrix keeps them in the desired location and orientation, acts as a load transfer medium between them. The principal fibers in commercial use are various types of glass fiber, carbon fiber, basalt fiber, Kevlar 49 and ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene and so on. FRP is a kind of strong, stiff, lightweight material for application to diverse structures, from aircraft, spacecraft and submarines to prosthetic device, civil structures, transport vehicles and so on.

In general, FRP materials have directional dependent properties with the directional dependence coming from the strength of the reinforced fiber. FRP can be produced which achieve good performance under tensile loads, while these parts are often not sufficiently ability to resist buckling or kinking in compression. In other words, the FRP is much softer and weaker in directions perpendicular to the stiff and strong direction. The weakness in compression limits the structural efficiency for FRP, therefore it is considered to be a design limiting parameter. In general, fibers are the principal load carrying members while the surrounding matrix keeps them in the desired location and orientation. The performance of compression depends on fiber misalignment, configuration of the fibers waviness, fiber types and so on^[1,2]. Compressive failure mode depends on the type of fiber, fiber volume fraction, thickness, fiber misalignment, configuration of fiber waviness and other factors. For unidirectional FRP, the fiber micro buckling failure mode is recognized as the dominant compressive failure mechanism. Than the potential relevance of a micro-buckling instability transition to kink band failure on compression in small volumes of a composite near defects, free edges or voids. It is assumed two possible buckling modes: an extensional mode and a shear mode, as shown in Figure.1. In composites of a significant fiber volume fraction, e.g., $V_f > 0.3$, the shear mode governs the compressive strength. Structure design of FRP using various techniques, like hybrid, stitching or modified resin were applied^[4]. In this study, a novel manner, named filament covering is proposed to improve the longitudinal compressive properties of unidirectional fiber reinforced plastic based on improving the compressive buckling critical load of FRP by preventing fiber buckling with a shortening of the buckling critical wavelength.

Figure 1: Micro buckling failure modes.(a)shear mode (b)Extensional mode

2 APPROACH

The present study attempted to develop new FRP materials with high compressive performance. In order to verify the enhance effect of filament cover proposal, UHMWPE fiber was choice to be the reinforced fiber, since this kind fiber reinforced FRP has relatively lower compressive performance. The UHMWPE fiber material used in this study was Dyneema SK60, which is produced by Toyobo Co., Ltd. Japan. Some fine fiber bundle with different tensile strength, elastic modulus, elongation at break were used as cover filament fibers. Four kind of filament fiber, basalt fiber, PBO fibers, UHMWPE fibers and PET fibers were choice (fig.2). The schematic diagram of covered fiber bundle was showed in fig.3.

Figure2: Preparation process of the test specimen

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of fiber covered bundle

Figure 4: Schematic of molding FRP sample by VaRTM

The covered UHMWPE fiber bundles with PBO fiber filament were prepared with a wind machine made by our laboratory. Epoxy resin (XNR6815) was used as the matrix of CFRP. Epoxy resin and hardener were 100 and 27 parts by weight. The covered UHMWPE bundle was prepared into fiber sheet with winding method. The FRP specimens employed for the tests were fabricated by VARTM (Vacuum assisted resin transfer molding) process, fig.4. The unidirectional UHMWPE FRP (UFRP) and PBO covered UHMWPE FRP (PBO/UFRP) were prepared. Depending on whether there is tension in the filament winding process, the specimen of PBO/UFRP were divided into two types, tension was exerted (PBO/UFRP1) and without exerted tension (PBO/UFRP2). Additionally, four groups specimen were prepared depended different filament. Named Dyneema/UFRP, PET/UFRP, Basalt/UFRP and PBO/UFRP, respectively. The size of the compression specimen was made conforming to the JIS-K 7076 of Japanese Industrial Standards. Compressive tests of the specimens were conducted by Auto Graph (AG-20KND) manufacture by Shimadzu Corporation.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fibrous impregnation with resin is an important technology in FRP fabrication. Although epoxy resin is a low viscosity as a thermosetting plastic make it could easily infiltrate fibers using VARTM method, after fiber bundle covered by filament with tension, the impregnation situation may not so optimism. So we observed the section of PBO/UFRP1 by scanning electron microscopy, to confirm the FRP internal impregnation status.

Figure 3: Micro-graph of section of PBO/UFRP1

As Fig.3 shows shows, the UHMWPE fiber bundles are closely aligned one by one and surrounded by resin. The yellow parts are covered PBO filaments. SEM picture in right indicates there is a well impregnation property for the winded UFRP since no voids between fibers.

Figure 4: Comparison of compressive strength and modulus of different specimens

The column fig.4 shows comparison for compressive strength and modulus of UFRP and PBO/UFRP, which in filament covering process with tension (PBO/UFRP2) and without tension (PBO/UFRP1). Compared with UFRP, the filament covering can improve the compressive strength about 15% for both PBO/UFRP1 and PBO/UFRP2. The existence of confinement limits the extent to which the fiber bundle buckling can deform. Simultaneously, a proportion of any applied load is carried by a change in tension in the PBO fiber. As a result, portion energy can be dissipated. Theoretically, the critical wavelength of fiber micro buckling is also being restricted, which cause the increase of critical buckling stress. For the compressive modulus, the specimen of PBO/UFRP1 increased approximate 45% comparison with the UFRP. While that of PBO/UFRP2 has no promotion. It means that the exerted tension has significant effect on the compressive modulus.

Tab.1. Properties of filament fiber

Properties	Units	UHMWPE	Basalt	PBO	Dyneema	PET
Density	g/cm ³	0.97	2.75	1.56	0.97	1.35
Tensile strength	MPa	2600	4840	5800	2600	1890
Elastic modulus	GPa	79	89	270	79	33
Elongation at break	%	4	3.15	2.5	4	6
Decitex	dtex	1320	330	273	55	90

Figure 5: Effect of filament type on the compression strength and modulus of PBO/UFRP

The influence of filament fibers on compressive strength properties has been presented in Fig.6, the mean values of compressive strength were found to range between 67.4 MPa for the PET filament covered UHMWPE fiber reinforced epoxy resin to 79.8 MPa for the basalt filament covered UHMWPE fiber reinforced epoxy resin with the higher compressive strength of covering filament being attributed to the superior compressive strength of covering filament, The result of this work is that the filament covering exhibited increase in compressive strength compared to the UHMWPE fiber reinforced FRP. While UHMWPE and PBO filament covered UFRP has significant increase, the compressive modulus have improved about 36% and 45% for Dyneema and PBO filament covered UFRP, respectively. These variables filament fibers having a significant influence on the compressive strength of FRP composites. The cover filament causes the UHMWPE bundles to have a higher buckling load, and the compressive force converted into the tensile force of filament fiber. The difference in filament fibers hybrid composite compression strength was attributed to the tensile strength, elastic modulus, elongation at break of filament fiber types.

4 CONCLUSION

Filament covered UHMWPE bundles with four kinds of filament were prepared, than the covered bundles were made into FRP. The results shows covered filament was found to affect the compressive properties of the composite. the compression properties and mechanism of compressive failure of the composites change with the filament types and exerted tensile at wind process.

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